

Notes

Complexes of Titanium(III), Titanium(IV) and Zirconium(IV) with 2-Thio-3-benzoylhydantoin

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SOLUTION and characterisation of Ti^{III} , Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} complexes with 2-thio-3-benzoylhydantoin has been described.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. or C.P. grade. The ligand, 2-thio-3-benzoylhydantoin was prepared by the procedure reported in literature¹.

Preparation of complexes: The Ti^{III} complex was prepared by distilling $TiCl_3$ and the ligand TBHNH in 1 : 3 ratio in dry benzene under nitrogen atmosphere for 8 h. A yellow precipitate appeared when the solution was vigorously stirred. The Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} complexes were prepared by heating 1 : 2 mixtures of the metal chloride and the ligand in benzene for 5–8 h on a steam-bath. Brown and yellow precipitate of Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} compounds separated on adjusting pH of the solutions to ≈ 8 . Precipitates were washed with ethanol, ether and finally dried under reduced pressure. All the three complexes were recrystallised from DMF.

Infrared spectra (KBr) in the range 4 000–200 cm^{-1} were recorded on a Perkin–Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (DMF) on a Perkin–Elmer 4000 A spectrophotometer, and ¹H nmr spectra on a EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer at R.S.I.C., Madras. Magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) values at room temperature (25°) were determined by Gouy method. The molar conductance of $10^{-2}M$ solutions of the complexes

in DMF at 25° was measured with a Systronics 03 conductivity meter. Analytical data are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Low molar conductance values (18.0–6.4 $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) of the complexes suggest their non-electrolytic nature.

The μ_{eff} value of the Ti^{III} complex (1.8 B.M.) corresponds to octahedral geometry². Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} complexes are diamagnetic.

In the infrared spectra of Ti^{III} , Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} complexes, ν_{NH} band (3 280 cm^{-1}) of the ligand³ disappeared, indicating coordination of the metal ions through deprotonated nitrogen in these complexes. The $\nu_{C=O}$ band at 1 690 cm^{-1} ($CH_2C=O$)^{4,5} in the free ligand shifted to lower frequency at 1 640–1 620 cm^{-1} , indicating coordination through this carbonyl oxygen in the Ti^{III} and Ti^{IV} complexes. The ligand band⁶ at 1 450 cm^{-1} shifted to lower frequency (1 420–1 400 cm^{-1}) in the Zr^{IV} complex, indicating coordination through sulphur. These bonding modes were further substantiated by the appearance of ν_{M-N} , ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-S} bands at 420–455, 480–510 and 315 cm^{-1} , respectively. Most probably higher effective nuclear charge of Zr^{IV} makes it effective to coordinate with S, and Ti^{III} and Ti^{IV} do not coordinate with S but with O of the ligand. In addition, bands at 345 and 380 cm^{-1} could be assigned to ν_{T-Oi} and ν_{Zr-Oi} modes. Since the band is unsplit, the chlorine atoms are present in *trans*-position in the complexes⁹.

A weak and broad band centred at 21 300 cm^{-1} for the Ti^{III} complex is in agreement with the octahedral geometry¹⁰. The Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} complexes show single charge transfer band at 24 750–24 600 and 24 850–24 360 cm^{-1} , respectively¹¹.

The NH proton signal of the ligand appearing to δ 10.6 ppm, is not observed in the complexes which confirms its deprotonation and coordination

TABLE 1 – ANALYTICAL AND M.P. DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)			
		M	N	S	Cl
$Ti(C_{10}H_7O_2N_2S)_2$	195	6.79 (6.76)	11.92 (11.87)	13.62 (13.57)	–
$Ti(C_{10}H_7O_2N_2S)_2Cl_2$	210	8.60 (8.52)	10.06 (10.00)	11.49 (11.41)	12.75 (12.68)
$Zr(C_{10}H_7O_2N_2S)_2Cl_2$	218	15.19 (15.00)	9.32 (9.28)	10.66 (10.59)	11.82 (11.80)

of nitrogen to the metal ions^{1,2}. The $\text{CH}_2\text{C}=\text{O}$ proton signal of the ligand at δ 2.58 shifted to δ 1.86 in the Ti^{III} and Ti^{IV} complexes due to coordination of the carbonyl oxygen of $\text{CH}_2\text{C}=\text{O}$ moiety to the metal ions^{1,2}. A multiplet centred at δ 7.0–9.0 due to the phenyl protons of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{C}=\text{O}$ moiety showing no shift, is observed in the complexes; this rules out the possibility of coordination through the carbonyl oxygen of this moiety.

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Synthesis and Characterisation of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes with some ONO Donor Schiff Bases

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THE synthesis and characterisation of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes with the potentially tridentate dibasic Schiff bases (1–4) are described in the present paper.

Substitution

- 1; H
- 2; 5- CH_3
- 3; 3- OCH_3
- 4; 5,6- C_6H_4

Experimental

The ligands 2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethylamine hydrochloride, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 5-methylsalicylaldehyde were obtained by Duff's method¹. The Schiff bases were prepared by the reaction of the amine (0.1 mol) and the corresponding aldehyde (0.1 mol) in ether and recrystallised from methanol.

Preparation of complexes: To an ethanol solution of the base hydrochloride (0.1 mol) and the corresponding aldehyde (0.1 mol), aqueous NaOH (0.3 mol) was added with vigorous stirring and the contents were kept on a water-bath until a clear reddish yellow solution was obtained. An ethanol solution of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was then added to it slowly with constant stirring and the resulting green or pinkish green precipitate was washed with ethanol and ether dried under reduced pressure.

Cobalt and nickel in the complexes were estimated gravimetrically² and nitrogen by Kjeldahl method. The molar conductance λ_m (in $10^{-3}M$ DMF), magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) values at room temperature, the electronic spectra and ir spectral data were recorded for characterising the complexes.

Results and Discussion

Cobalt(II) complexes are pinkish green whereas the nickel(II) complexes are yellowish green. Both the cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in solvents like DMF and DMSO. The results of elemental analysis (Table 1) show that the complexes have 1:1 (metal:ligand) stoichiometry indicating the tridentate dibasic behaviour of the Schiff bases. Low molar conductances of the complexes in DMF indicate their non-electrolytic nature³.

The cobalt(II) complexes show two *d-d* bands in 17 000–18 000 and 24 000–26 000 cm^{-1} regions which may be attributed to transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(g)$ (ν_1) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_2), respectively. The ν_1 was not observed due to instrumental limitation. However ν_1 was calculated by the method (C)⁴ using the calculated values of $10 Dq$ and B . The values of transitions ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 may be obtained by König's equations⁵. The ligand field parameter B and the ligand field splitting energy ($10 Dq$) in case of the cobalt(II) complexes were calculated⁶. Out of the four methods